

GINNNGER

From Barriers to Action

Policy Insights for Advancing Urban
Regeneration in **Bulgaria**

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About GINNGER

The GINNGER project aims to create new, inclusive and participatory processes for **neighbourhood regeneration**. A **methodology** to support collaborative **decision-making** is at the project's core. GINNGER is also designing and implementing regeneration plans across six pilot sites in Europe. Four key areas of regeneration are involved: energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources and sustainable mobility.

**GINNGER | Co-designing
neighbourhood regeneration**

The Bulgarian policy context

Sustainable and inclusive **neighbourhood regeneration** is shaped by various European hard- and soft-law instruments. However, translating these EU objectives into practice often faces **fragmented competencies** across governance levels, limited integration of **participatory processes** in planning and limited **administrative capacity** at the municipal level.

Bulgarian legislation on this topic includes:

- Energy Efficiency Act (2015).¹
- Spatial Development Act.²
- National Programme for Energy Efficiency of Multi-family Buildings.³

Barriers, Opportunities and Recommendations

	Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of legal mechanisms for social inclusion and co-creation in neighbourhood regeneration. • Contrasting norms and complex procedures that regulate actions, instruments and processes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak integration of circular construction principles in local policies. • Limited local administrative capacity and financial and technical support.
	Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active transposition of EU directives on building performance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong national support for large-scale renovation funding.
	Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop citizen-engagement practices to stimulate the implementation of collaborative and people-oriented solutions. • Establish a clear definition of energy communities that aligns with EU directives, and provide guidance for municipalities and citizens on the rights, responsibilities and benefits of participation in energy communities. Reinforce technical and financial support at the local level. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accelerate the implementation of the national building renovation programme, prioritising funding and administrative capacity for large-scale renovation projects, set measurable milestones for achieving national energy efficiency targets and simplify application procedures to increase participation. • Fast-track the national decarbonisation plan, launching targeted measures for single-family homes to improve insulation, heating systems and renewable energy integration; provide financial incentives and technical support for adopting energy-efficient solutions.

Conclusions and next steps

The recommendations presented are **based on GIUNGER's pilots of Plovdiv's experience**. They aim to support authorities and policymakers to facilitating and standardising neighbourhood renovation and collaborative decision-making at the national and local level. During the next months, the project partners will expand this analysis, identifying **best practices and potential areas for harmonisation** in all pilot sites and in all four key areas of regeneration (energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources, and sustainable mobility).

Methodology

The analysis presented was based on data collected through the assessment of policy and regulatory drivers and barriers (conducted under GIUNGER's Task 2.4), and through questionnaires circulated among pilot partners.

Sources and further information

¹ [SEEA Government Document](#)

² [SPATIAL DEVELOPMENT ACT | MRDPW](#)

³ [Energy Efficiency of Multi-Family Residential Buildings National Programme](#)

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